

Analysis of the experience of functioning of anti-crisis mechanisms in the economies of developed countries of the world and Russia

E.Yu. Khrustalev,

д-р экон. наук, проф., главный научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: staley777@yandex.ru)

S.N. Larin,

канд. техн. наук, ведущий научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: sergey77707@rambler.ru)

O.E. Khrustalev,

канд. экон. наук, старший научный сотрудник, Центральный экономико-математический институт РАН (e-mail: oleg.khrustalev@gmail.com)

Аннотация. При анализе текущего состояния и особенностей развития мировой и отечественной экономик в условиях распространения глобальных кризисных явлений важно учитывать имеющийся опыт их преодоления. В статье особое внимание уделено изучению и разработке перспективных антикризисных механизмов, предназначенных для стабилизации и укрепления российской экономики. Представлен анализ стратегических антикризисных планов укрепления и развития территорий, транспорта, банковской системы, науки и образования. Выполнена системная оценка антикризисных инноваций и государственных расходов, а также антикризисных возможностей международных компаний, в которых участвуют отечественные предприятия.

Abstract. The article analyzes the state and features of global and domestic economic progress taking place in the context of the spread of global crisis phenomena. Special attention is paid to the study and development of promising anti-crisis mechanisms designed to stabilize and strengthen the Russian economy. Based on the experience of economically developed countries, strategic anti-crisis plans for strengthening and developing territories, transport, the banking system, science, and education are proposed. The systematic assessment of anti-crisis innovations, government spending, and anti-crisis capabilities of international companies in which domestic enterprises participate has been carried out.

Ключевые слова: экономический кризис, антикризисные механизмы, инновации, наукоемкие и высокотехнологичные предприятия, квалифицированные кадры, импортная продукция, банковская система.

Keywords: anti-crisis mechanisms, economic crisis, innovations, knowledge-intensive and high-tech enterprises, qualified personnel, imported products, banking system.

Introduction

In the middle of the last century, an international financial and economic market environment was formed, one of the characteristics of which was the emergence of global crisis processes [15]. Due to economic and financial crises, the national income of the state is decreasing and unemployment and bankruptcy are observed, which significantly worsens the living conditions of the population even in developed countries. Usually, crises stretch into a depressive phase, which also lasts for a long time, slowing down economic growth and scientific and technological progress.

The global crisis that occurred in 2008–2009 and the subsequent multiyear recession revealed the main causes of the crisis. In order to eliminate and neutralize these causes, joint and coordinated actions of many countries were needed, as well as the transition to a new innovative technological order.

The available economic statistical figures convincingly demonstrate that crises are becoming longer and deeper, and this fact forces the development and practical application of progressive methods and mechanisms to prevent their occurrence.

During crisis periods, the effective actions of various anti-crisis mechanisms are improved, expanded, and noticeably strengthened [2], which makes it possible to reduce the negative consequences of a sharp decline in industrial production and protect national markets.

Anti-crisis mechanisms in the economies of developed countries

To combat crisis processes, many leading countries of the world are developing and practically implementing strategic anti-crisis plans [1]. For example, anti-crisis mechanisms are being created in many American states in accordance with the US strategic plan, which is designed to support housing and infrastructure construction, as well as mortgages [6].

During the 2008–2009 crisis, the U.S. Senate and Congress approved a nearly 1,000-page plan worth \$787 billion on stimulating and innovative development of the American economy. Most of the developed plan was related to the real estate market. It proposed effective methods for solving mortgage problems that increase housing affordability, infrastructure renovation, and the development of projects

related to alternative energy and territorial development.

During this crisis period, the US Federal Reserve System began the practical implementation of a program to repurchase securities and direct obligations of mortgage brokers, the planned implementation of which was scheduled to be completed within a year. Prohibiting the alienation of residential buildings, easing the burden of payments to mortgage borrowers, stabilizing the balance sheets of financial institutions, and stimulating the issuance of new loans were planned to support the real estate market.

American citizens have received the opportunity to renew their loans to cheaper ones with reduced interest rates. The support plan also assumed that the bank that issued the loan would voluntarily reduce loan rates for borrowers who were facing alienation of housing, and the government would pay the bank a financial reward for each reissued mortgage agreement.

In this part of the plan, there was also a legislative initiative that allowed courts to review the terms of the mortgage for borrowers, who owned the only house and have become insolvent. In the decision-making process, the judges were able to increase the time period of lending, reduce interest rates, as well as bring the main amount of debt in line with the "fair" housing price.

This plan also helped to prevent an increase in interest rates and to encourage large financial institutions to issue new mortgage loans for the purchase of residential premises by citizens. In order to successfully achieve this goal, the banks were financed additionally.

Anti-crisis spending on the development of transport, territories, education and supporting the living standards of the country's population.

The plans of economically developed countries provide for the allocation of significant financial resources for the development of transport infrastructure, which in many countries is severely worn out. One of the main strategic directions is the further development of the high-speed highway system. A significant part of the state budget is spent on these new highways. The governments of many countries allocate billions of dollars to create high-speed railway systems and hubs, as well as modern freight and passenger intermodal terminals. Such terminals are capable of performing combined transportation and have a synergistic effect arising from the combination of automobile, aviation, and railway cargo and passenger flows at one transport point. Such a new transport center has been built, in particular, in Miami.

The United States directly allocates about 2% of the anti-crisis plan total costs to the real estate market. Most of these funds are distributed among specific regional projects. The remaining funds are allocated to support energy-saving projects and to implement programs to reduce and eliminate the negative effects of various destabilizing effects.

The plan adopted by the US Congress to stimulate the country's economy is not only a plan to combat the current crisis. But also a kind of bridge that is being built into the future, since the old technologies (from the 19th and 20th centuries) are no longer working, and the railways built in the middle of the 20th century should be replaced by more efficient modern ones. The same applies to the means of transmitting information and electricity. Besides, new sources of energy are emerging. The plan will also present the best educational opportunities for the United States to be competitive in the future.

In order to provide people with jobs and at the same time reduce dependence on foreign oil, it was proposed to invest money in the production of renewable energy resources and the modernization of public buildings; \$35 billion was allocated to make their maintenance less costly; \$22 billion was spent on science and advanced technologies. Rebuilding roads has cost Americans \$22 billion. Another \$20 billion was spent on solving environmental problems.

The cost of education in the form of tax subsidies to schools and colleges, tax deductions to citizens, and financing of many educational programs amounted to \$85.2 billion. \$21 billion was allocated for the support and modernization of medical institutions, which made it possible to reduce prices for medical services and improve the health of citizens.

Those who lost a job were provided with tax deductions, as well as the opportunity to learn a new profession and find a new job. Also, certain debt restructuring programs were promised to mortgage debtors.

Other developed countries have also made significant interventions in the economy. Thus, in Japan, the volume of measures to stimulate the economy amounted to \$110 billion, and in Germany – more than \$70 billion. At the same time, such stimulation of domestic demand turned out to be insufficient. The decline in GDP in these countries was significant: in Germany, it was 6%, and in Japan 6.1%. In addition, the economic situation in Germany affected the results of the entire Euro area, where GDP is forecasted to decline by 4.4%, as well as production in Eastern European countries, a significant share of whose exports are destined for the German market.

However, in Eastern Europe, those countries that have managed to attract foreign investment into their industry are in a relatively shallow recession. For example, Poland's GDP fell by 0.8% in 2009, the Czech Republic by 3%, and Slovakia by 5% [3].

Innovative advances in the Russian economy

The Russian economy has also experienced many crises in recent decades, the most noticeable slowdowns in its development were observed, in particular, at the beginning of the 21st century [9, 10]. During this period, the most difficult problems arose in science-intensive and high-tech industries, which is confirmed, for example, by the financial and economic analysis of the state of rocket and space industries and markets [7, 13]. Anti-crisis mechanisms

in this area of industrial and commercial activity were associated with the construction and practical use of models and methods of their innovative development and financial reliability [4, 11, 16].

The Ministry of Industry and Trade of Russia, like many countries in crisis conditions, divided the future car market into two components in the economic development project: one of them will sell domestic, and the other – imported automotive equipment. The share of Russian products should not be less than 52%, and the Government of the Russian Federation places the main bet on two car assembly plants: Renault-AvtoVAZ and Sollers-Fiat. The new legislative document represents a logical improvement of the Automotive Industry Innovative Development Concept, approved by the government back in 2012. However, currently, the main problem being solved is the post-crisis recovery and expansion of industrial production, as well as the transition to a domestic component base (accelerated implementation of import substitution processes).

The maximum goal is to increase the contribution of the automotive industry to GDP from today's 1.2% to 3% by 2025. To successfully solve this problem, the country needs to produce about 4 million passenger cars per year, while the number of imported cars should not exceed the twenty percent barrier. The total cost of implementing this strategy is estimated at 2÷2,6 trillion rubles. The main domestic producers will have to spend about 690 billion rubles. The remaining financial investments should be made by foreign car construction companies.

At the same time, it was decided to reduce the volume of financing for the automotive industry to 1÷1,2 trillion rubles. Funds planned for the purchase of foreign assets (about 150 billion rubles) were taken out of the program), and estimates of investments by Russian companies in the industry decreased to 584 billion rubles. New technical regulations were also required and developed in order to meet international safety and environmental requirements. Meanwhile, maximum attention was paid to improving competitiveness, since the main strategic goal was to create a competitive automotive industry in Russia that would be able to implement the entire complex technological chain – from metal to a modern domestic car.

Organization of international companies with the participation of Russian enterprises

As a result of special research, it was found that the lag in labor productivity at Russian enterprises from foreign analogs can be eliminated by improving business processes. However, the main task is still to develop new technological innovations that are created on the basis of achievements in science and technology and are new to the market. One of the possible methods to solve this problem is based on the processes of implementation by domestic enterprises of specific developments in the production field together with advanced foreign companies.

Car industry. In 2010, the Swedish company Scania began production of trucks in Russia at its

plant near St. Petersburg. It allowed Russian consumers to receive trucks quickly, since the factory has a large warehouse of components from which cars can be quickly assembled upon receipt of an order. There was also a decrease in the price of trucks, as they were no longer subject to customs duties on cargo chassis imported into Russia.

In 2007, construction of a new automobile plant began in the village of Kamenka, where the first car was released two years later. More than \$200 million was allocated for the construction, and after its final completion, the plant began to produce 50,000 cars per year (two models: Nissan Teana and Nissan X-Trail). This project provided jobs for 750 people at the plant and about 5,000 more as suppliers, logistics workers, etc.

Aviation. VSMPO-AVISMA Corporation, which became part of the Rostechology State Corporation, and the American Boeing Corporation decided to organize a joint production company Ural Boeing Manufacturing in the Sverdlovsk Region in 2007. Currently, this industrial enterprise, equipped with innovative technologies and tools, is successfully engaged in processing titanium stampings for Russian airlines and the most modern civil aviation aircraft Boeing 787.

This multinational company successfully and effectively solves complex production problems, using the achievements of fundamental and applied science and meeting all the requirements of international quality standards.

Ural Boeing Company performs primary mechanical processing of bulk titanium stampings manufactured by VSMPO-AVISMA Corporation. Processing is being completed at the American Boeing plant in Portland. In addition, titanium chips, which are formed during machining, are immediately returned to VSMPO-AVISMA for processing, which will create a unique closed-cycle chain to support the production of titanium semi-finished products, stampings, and other types of products.

Metallurgy. In the Chelyabinsk Region, work is underway to set up and adjust equipment at the largest project of South Ural metallurgists of the last decade. A new sheet rolling mill "Stan 5000" has been tested at the Magnitogorsk Iron and Steel Works. It is unique in its characteristics not only in Russia but also abroad and is capable of producing competitive import-substituting products that are widely in demand in the market.

The United Metallurgical Company, which for the first time in the history of domestic industry received an order for the manufacture of pipes, connecting parts, and pipe fittings intended for the construction of the underwater gas pipeline Nord Stream – 2, successfully performs all necessary production work. Over the years, the company has supplied the required number of very large diameter pipes to create this long gas pipeline.

Currently, the Vyksa Plant, which is part of the United Metallurgical Company, is the only domestic plant producing large-diameter metal pipes that meet the most stringent international requirements. This

plant was the first in Russia to occupy an underwater market niche, which allowed it to become a participant in global and domestic oil and gas projects, since most of the pipelines are located in offshore zones at the bottom of oceans and seas. High production and commercial results were achieved due to multibillion-dollar investments and scientific and production activities carried out by the company for technical re-equipment and modernization of pipe production, through the introduction of an innovative management system brought into line with the latest international standards, as well as through professional development of workers and employees of the company.

Power tools. At the end of 2008, a joint Russian-Chinese enterprise was established under the name Interskol Crown Group (Interskol). It is the sixth company in the world in terms of production of power tools. Its activities are based on the interaction of the Russian engineering school of power tools, one of the strongest in the world, and the ability of the Chinese to produce a mass product quickly and cheaply.

This multinational company has maintained a stable position in all business components from the development of new models and their production to sales to the end consumer. No company in the industry has such an integrated system today. The immediate tasks of the partners are to strengthen the position of the Interskol brand in the Russian and CIS markets, mainly through the development of the markets for Azerbaijan and Kazakhstan.

The example of Interskol was followed by other Russian companies with a strong engineering school and a good reputation in local markets. Having at their disposal a production base and Chinese workforce, our technological productions successfully maintain and develop their school, and also create opportunities for themselves to enter new markets.

Banking system. Russian banks are not staying away from the positive movement in the industry. The domestic banking system actively creates and uses anti-crisis mechanisms [5], financial and industrial groups [14], and modern methods of increasing bank credit potential [8]. Back in October 2009, the Supervisory Board of Vnesheconombank decided to extend loans for a year to all borrowers who requested it. According to the chairman of this bank, six companies took advantage of this opportunity, including UC Rusal, Evraz Group, Gazprom Neft, PIK, and others. All of them received loans to refinance loans from foreign banks. Since then, new loan agreements with debtors have been signed by the bank on market terms.

Conclusion

Global experience shows that anti-crisis innovations can be created by small and medium-sized companies, since large structures are not prone to the risk associated with a technological breakthrough. In the USA, which is considered a technological world leader, 75% of new jobs are created by small and medium-sized businesses, as well as 70% of discoveries and inventions, 75% of rich Americans also work in this field.

In Russia, the insufficient activity of some research centers and higher educational institutions, which spend a significant part of the scientific budget, leads to the fact that innovative anti-crisis modernization is carried out at a slow pace. The scientific community should improve the skills of its employees with the help of new intelligent educational systems [12] and demand attention to its needs. This will increase the prestige of science and attract capable young people to scientific activities, the results of which will be scientific justification and the creation of new effective anti-crisis mechanisms.

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